

HISTORICAL DEVELOPING THE GREAT SILK ROAD

Karimova Madina Saydulla kizi

Associate Professor of Andijan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11216560>

Annotation. In this article, the Great Silk Road, which has served in economic, political, social, and trade exchanges for many years in the history of mankind, the creation of the trade route and its current state, and the Great Silk Road, which has played an important role in the history of this route of our country, is presented. Historical information about the development of the Great Silk Road is given. From the 2nd century BC to the 15th century AD, it served as a link between the East and the West for thousands of years. It has served mankind for many years as an important tool in historical civilization relations.

Key words: Silk, Great, Pass, China, Richthofen, transit, communication, gas, Central Asia, World trade route.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada insoniyat tarixidagi uzoq yillar mobaynida iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ijtimoiy, savdo-sotiq sohasida o'zaro almashinuvida xizmat qilgan, savdo yo'lining vujudga kelishi va bugungi kundagi holati, yurtimizning ushbu yo'l tarixida muhim o'rin tutgan Buyuk ipak yo'li rivojlanishi haqidagi tarixiy ma'lumotlar berilgan. Buyuk ipak yo'li mil.avv.II asrdan to milodiy XV asrgacha, ming yillar davomida Sharq va G'arb o'rtasidagi aloqalarda xizmat qilgan. Buyuk ipak yo'li ko'pgina davlatlarning tarixiy svilizatsion aloqalarida muhim vosita sifatida, insoniyatga uzoq yillar mobaynida xizmat qilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Ipak, Buyuk, Dovon, Xitoy, Rixtgofen, tranzit, muloqot, gazlama, O'rta Osiyo, Jahon savdo yo'li.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются Великий Шелковый путь, служивший на протяжении многих лет в истории человечества экономическим, политическим, социальным и торговым обменам, созданию торгового пути и его нынешнему состоянию, а также Великий Шелковый путь, который сыграл важную роль в истории этого маршрута нашей страны, приводятся исторические сведения о развитии Великого Шелкового пути. Со II века до нашей эры по XV век нашей эры он служил связующим звеном между Востоком и Востоком. Западу на протяжении тысячелетий он служил человечеству важным инструментом в исторических цивилизационных отношениях.

Ключевые слова: Шелк, Великий, Перевал, Китай, Рихтгофен, транзит, связь, газ, Средняя Азия, Мировой торговый путь.

The Great Silk Road is a trade route that connected the East and the West in ancient times, a unique event in the history of human development, its desire to unite and exchange cultural values, to reach markets for the sale of products and living space. Before sea and ocean routes were opened, these roads gained importance.

Movement is life, travel, globalization has always been the driving force of development. This intercontinental trade route, the largest in human history, connected Europe and Asia and in the past stretched from the ancient Roman state to Nara, the ancient capital of Japan. Of course, trade between the East and the West had been carried on since ancient times, sunk in the depths of the past, but these were isolated parts of the future Great Road. The formation of trade relations was greatly helped by the discovery and mining of semi-precious stones in the mountains of Central Asia - lapis lazuli, nephrite, agate, and turquoise, which are highly valued in the East. For

example, there was a "lazurite road" that supplied lapis lazuli from Central Asia to Iran, Mesopotamia and even Egypt. At the same time, the "jade road" was formed, which connected Khotan and Yorkend districts with the regions of North China. In addition, agate stones were brought to the countries of East Asia from Sogdiana and Bactria, and turquoise was brought from Khorezm. All these directions eventually merged into the Great Silk Road. Historians believe that the real beginning of the great road, which connected the caravan routes from Central Asia to the West and South, and the roads leading from China to Eastern Turkestan, is in the middle of the second century BC.

It was the first intercontinental caravan route that connected Eastern and Western countries in ancient and medieval times (2nd century BC - 15th century AD). The term Great Silk Road is associated with the valuable product transported along this route - Chinese silk. Western countries have been ignorant of the secrets of silk production for a long time.

The term Great Silk Road was not used in ancient times. The scientific study of the historical, geographical and cultural aspects of the Great Silk Road was actually started by the scientists of many countries in the second half of the 19th century. Scientists from Western Europe, Russia and Japan made a significant contribution to its research. In particular, "Encyclopedia of the Great Silk Road" was published in Japan. In 1877, the famous German scientist Karl Richthofen in his major scientific work "China" called the system of roads connecting different parts of the huge Eurasian continent "Silk Road", later the term "Great Silk Road" was adopted.

Even before the 2nd century BC, there were connections between the East and the West through the Central Asian caravan routes. An example of this can be the objects made in Asia Minor, found in the Poziryk fortress in the Altai Mountains, and the Greek objects found in Afghanistan and Central Asia. With the establishment of the kingdom of Alexander the Great (see Alexander the Great), these relations were put on the right track. The Sugdians played a major role in the establishment of the eastern part of the Great Silk Road. With the conquest of the Sugdian country by Alexander the Great, many Sugdians moved to the east and built trade factories (locations) in the central part of the Great Silk Road - from Central Asia to the Chinese city of Chanan. In turn, the Han Empire at the end of the 1st millennium BC pursued a policy of expanding its territory towards Central Asia, paying special attention to this direction and sending the ambassador Zhang Xiang to gather information about this route, for espionage and diplomatic purposes. However, the first detailed route from Hierapolis, east of the Mediterranean Sea in Syria, to Serica (China) was made by the Macedonian merchant Mai Titian (100 AD). This information is stored in Claudius Ptolemy's "Geographic Manual". Ptolemy, in turn, obtained this information from the works of the historian Marin, written between 107 and 114 years and which have not reached us. According to these data, the Great Silk Road is divided into 2 layers: from Hierapol to Tashminor (Tashkurgan) and from Tashminor to Serika. The Central Asian part of the road started from Aria (the ancient region located in the south of present-day Turkmenistan and the north-west of Afghanistan). From Aria, the road went north to Antiochia in Margiyana (the ruins of the ancient city of Marv near the city of Bairamali), and then turned east to Bactra (the city of Balkh in northern Afghanistan). From here, the road headed north, crossed Amudarya around Termiz, and then went in 2 directions.

The first one went along the northern one through the Iron Gate to Morocco (Samarkand), and from there to Fergana. The second one in the south led along the Surkhandarya valley to the mountainous land of the Comedians (now Karategin). Both directions lead to Tashminor. Some scientists believe that it is located in the Tashkent region, others in the Olay Valley. After

Tashminor, the road went out of the territory of Central Asia, around Ergashtom there was a "trader's settlement", then the road passed through the Takla Makon desert to Dunhuang, and then to Chanan, the ancient capital of China. From here, the road probably went northwest to Korea and Japan. In the 5th-8th centuries AD, the northern part of the Great Silk Road through Yettisuv to Choch (Tashkent oasis), Sughd, then Poykend, Marv to Iran's Khurasan became important. At the same time, in connection with the ban on silk transportation to Byzantium through Iran, Sughd merchants, through the mediation of Byzantine and Turkish khans, opened a new road network from Sughd and Khorezm, bypassing the Caspian Sea, passing through the passes in the North Caucasus, to the Black Sea and then to Constantinople. With the help of silk, which was highly rated in the West and equaled in value to gold and precious stones, the Byzantine emperors recruited warriors from Europe and won over the rulers of the neighboring "barbarian" - Germanic and Slavic tribes, because silk was considered more valuable to them. At this time, silk became an object of economic competition between 3 great powers: the Byzantine Empire, Sassanid Iran and the great Turkic Khanate. However, this "silk" route apparently did not exist for long, as China lost its monopoly on silk production in the second half of the 6th century, and by the end of the century Byzantium was producing so much silk that there was no need to import it from China. The history of the Great Silk Road ends with the establishment of the Byzantine silk industry and its gradual spread to the countries of the Caucasus and the Mediterranean. In the following centuries, especially during the reign of the Mongols, although there is a lot of evidence that there was a caravan route connecting the East and the West, the name "silk road" can be conditionally applied to it, because the importance of this road was no longer marked by silk, but by other goods and purposes.

In 1987, UNESCO adopted the international program "Silk Road - Road of Communication" as part of the UN Decade for Cultural Development. This program provides a comprehensive study of the rich cultural history of the peoples of Central Asia. However, its main goal is to establish stronger cultural and economic ties between the East and the West, to improve relations between the numerous peoples living on these great continents. Many (more than 30) international scientific conferences (including Samarkand, October 1990; Bukhara, February 1996) and seminars were held. The Great Silk Road joint international expeditions were organized, films were made, books, brochures and articles were published, some archaeological and architectural monuments were repaired. In some Eastern countries (India, China, Uzbekistan, Sri Lanka, Japan), special scientific institutes have been established to study the Great Silk Road. According to the decision of Maye, UN and UNESCO, the International Institute of Central Asian Studies was opened in Samarkand. In May 1997, the construction of the Sarakhs-Mashhad railway section connecting Central Asia with Iran was completed, thus Central Asian countries had access to the Persian Gulf, and European countries had access to Central Asia. In addition to scientific and cultural programs, a project of global importance is being implemented to restore the Great Silk Road (see Europe-Caucasus-Asia Transport Corridor (TRACECA)). The next task is to build a railway section between Uzbekistan and China. If this plan is implemented, the "railway" option of the Great Silk Road from the Atlantic Ocean to the Pacific Ocean will be fully restored.

In conclusion, we can say that by the end of the 1st millennium BC and the beginning of the 1st millennium AD, the culture of a huge geographical area stretching from the Pacific Ocean to the Atlantic Ocean unites into a single system of highly developed civilizations. The borders of the states located in this area - the Han Dynasty in China, the Kushan Kingdom, the Kang State, the Parthian State, and the Roman Empire were adjacent to each other. The centers of these great

kingdoms and civilizations were connected for the first time in human history by a road known as the Great Silk Road. A total length of 12,000 km, stretching from China to the northern shores of the Mediterranean Sea, many nations and peoples have established various relations. It became a tradition for the kings to send ambassadors to each other, to give each other gifts. The influence of Eastern and Western cultures on each other increased. As a result, many of the cultural similarities of that time also appeared.

REFERENCES

1. National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan Volume I. Tashkent 2005. p. 814
2. History of Uzbekistan - R.H. Murtozoyev. Tashkent. 2005. p. 96-101.
3. The Great Silk Road-A. Khojayev. Tashkent. 2007/page 146
4. Historical memories-Sima Yan, Sima Chyan. Chapter 130/Chapter 17; page 54.
5. History of the Han Dynasty -Ban Gu. Chapter 200/Chapter 67; pp. 67-75.
6. Ancient period- B. Boymenov, U. Shoimov, F. Bozorboyev, F. Sultanov, Sh. Yod Gorov, Tashkent/2006. Pages 149-150.
7. The great silk road - a way of communication and cooperation- Og'abek Bahriddin o'g'li Mamayusupov. Central Asian Research journal.2022